

Effect of Kethoxal Treatment on the Capacities of Ribosomal RNAs to form Bimolecular Complex

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That 16S and 23S RNAs form a specific binary complex is indicative of RNA-RNA interaction in ribosomal subunit association. More direct evidences have been provided here following the important observation made by Noller and his coworkers that the treatment of ribosomal subunits with kethoxal, a guanine-specific reagent, leads to the loss of their association capacity. Interestingly enough, 16S and 23S RNAs isolated from treated subunits as well lose their capacities to form RNA-RNA complex. Even when naked 16S and 23S RNAs are individually treated with kethoxal they also lose their association capacities as it happens when they are derived from kethoxal-treated subunits. Noller and coworkers have already shown that the modifiable guanine bases of rRNAs are protected against kethoxal treatment in 70S ribosomes. As shown in the present work, RNAs isolated from kethoxal-treated 70S ribosomes also retain their association capacity. Similarly, when the 16S,23S RNA complex is treated with kethoxal the individual RNAs retain most (about 89%) of their association capacities. These results clearly indicate that 16S,23S complex formation reflects the mechanism of association of 30S and 50S ribosomes and therefore, RNA-RNA interaction must play major role in the subunit association. The present studies led to another interesting finding that 50S ribosomes occur in two different conformations and that due to differences in conformations of 23S RNAs. These results have been discussed elsewhere.

THE demonstration that 16S and 23S ribosomal RNAs from a binary complex under certain specific conditions¹⁻⁴ and the complex can be stabilised by psoralen crosslinking⁵, raised the obvious question whether RNA-RNA interaction plays a major role in the association of ribosomal subunits. Several workers (in Ref. 1) postulated that such interaction is quite likely but no direct evidence was available. It has been further shown in this laboratory that 5S RNA is incorporated into such complex and that also in stoichiometric amount only when the ribosomal proteins implicated in its binding to 50S ribosome are present⁶. The initiation factor 3 (IF3) which is known to dissociate 70 ribosomes, also dissociates 16S,23S RNA complex, although partially, to its constituents⁶. The most interesting finding in this laboratory is that 16S,23S RNA complex displays ribosome like activities although the activities are comparatively much weaker than those of ribosomes^{7,8}.

Kethoxal (β -ethoxy- α -ketobutyraldehyde) which specifically modifies guanine bases⁹ has been extensively used in the study of the structure of nucleic acids. The sites of reaction of kethoxal with 16S RNA in intact 30S ribosomal subunit were identified by Noller¹⁰ with the help of a new diagonal electrophoresis method. The same reagent was used to study the accessibility of specific sites in the 16S RNA in 30S as well as 70S ribosomes and the guanine residues protected by 50S ribosomes from kethoxal modification were identified^{11,12}. Similarly, the protection of specific sites in 23S and 5S RNAs from kethoxal modification by association of 30S

and 50S subunits were also investigated^{13,14}. These studies hinted at the distinct possibility that certain regions of 16S and 23S RNAs are involved in Watson-Crick type base pairing or other ways during the association of ribosomal subunits. The same reagent has been extensively used in this laboratory to show that 50S ribosomes occur in two distinct conformations (tight couple and loose couple) and that due to difference in conformations of 23S RNAs in the two types of ribosomes^{15,16}. In case the association of naked 16S and 23S RNAs reflects the mechanism of subunit association, kethoxal treatment of ribosomes and subunits as well as rRNAs is expected to provide some useful information. The results obtained by such approach as documented below, indicate that the sites of rRNAs implied in the association of ribosomal subunits are most likely involved in the association of naked ribosomal RNAs as well.

Experimental

Buffers: TMA buffer contained 10 mM tris-HCl, pH 7.5, 10 mM magnesium acetate and 30 mM ammonium chloride. TEM buffer contained 100 mM triethanolamine-HCl, pH 7.0 and 10 mM magnesium chloride. The reconstitution (R) buffer contained 20 mM tris-HCl, pH 7.5, 400 mM KCl and 20 mM magnesium acetate as described earlier¹, whereas the modified reconstitution (R') buffer contained the above components except that 20 mM tris-HCl, pH 7.5, was replaced with 100 mM triethanolamine-HCl, pH 7.5. RNA dissociating (D) buffer con-

tained 10 mM tris-HCl, pH 7.5, 100 mM KCl and 1 mM EDTA.

Isolation of ribosomes and ribosomal RNAs: *E. coli* 70S, 50S and 30S ribosomes were prepared as described earlier¹⁷. Ribosomal RNAs (16S and 23S) were prepared from the respective subunits by treatment with phenol in presence of sodium dodecyl sulphate followed by precipitation with ethanol as described by Amils *et al.*¹⁸. The 23S RNA was freed from 5S RNA by gel filtration through Sephadex G-100 according to the method of Erdman *et al.*¹⁹. ³²P-labelled 30S and 50S ribosomes were prepared from *E. coli* grown in ³²P-containing medium. ³²P-labelled 16S and 23S RNAs were prepared from the subunits by the same procedure as described above.

Treatment of 70S, 50S and 30S ribosomes with kethoxal: Ribosomal preparation in TMA were dialysed against TEM for 12 h prior to kethoxal treatment. The treatment was carried out in TEM (1 ml) containing kethoxal (Upjohn Company, U.S.A.) (4 mg) and ribosomes (6 mg). The mixture was incubated at 37° for 1 h and then chilled to 0°. The excess kethoxal was removed by precipitation with 0.7 volume of ethanol at -20°. The precipitate was dissolved in minimum volume of TMA and dialysed against the same for 6 h at 0°.

Treatment of 16S, 23S RNAs and the 16S.23S RNA complex with kethoxal: The treatment was carried out either in TEM buffer or under reconstitution condition¹. However, the reconstitution (R') buffer contained triethanolamine instead of tris to avoid reaction with kethoxal. The replacement of tris with triethanolamine does not affect the complex formation between 16S and 23S RNAs. ³²P-labelled 16S or 23S RNA or equimolar mixture of the two was dialysed against TEM or R' buffer before treatment with kethoxal. Then 4 mg of each type of RNA (1.4 mg of 16S plus 2.6 mg of 23S in case of mixture) were treated with kethoxal in the same buffer for 1 h at 37° and then excess kethoxal was removed by dialysing the sample against R buffer.

Density gradient centrifugation: The density gradient centrifugation was carried out at 100 000 g for 6 h in swing out rotor of a Beckman L5-50B ultracentrifuge. The detailed procedure has been described earlier¹.

Results

Effect of the kethoxal treatment of 30S and 50S subunits on their association capacities: As discussed in the introduction, Noller and his coworkers¹⁰⁻¹⁴ have already demonstrated that modification of guanine residues of 16S and 23S RNAs at the interface of the two subunits leads to the loss of their capacity to associate with each other to form 70S ribosomes. Similar experiments have been carried out here by treating 30S and 50S subunits individually with kethoxal and testing

their capacities to associate with each other by density gradient centrifugation. The results are shown in Fig. 1. Untreated 30S and 50S subunits associate with each other at 10 mM Mg²⁺ ion concentration. However, when both the subunits are

Fig. 1. Effect of kethoxal treatment on the association capacities of 30S and 50S ribosomes. Both 50S and 30S ribosomes were treated separately with kethoxal. Following ethanol precipitation, ribosomes were dissolved in and dialysed against TMA containing 10 mM Mg²⁺. Either type of 50S ribosomes (treated or untreated, 30 A₂₆₀ units) were separately mixed with equimolar amount of 30S ribosomes (as indicated below) in TMA containing 10 mM Mg²⁺ and individually subjected to sucrose density gradient (5-30%) centrifugation. The gradient contained the same buffer. Symbol: (A) untreated 50S and 30S ribosomes, (B) untreated 50S and treated 30S ribosomes, (C) treated 50S and untreated 30S ribosomes, and (D) treated 50S and 30S ribosomes.

treated individually with kethoxal their association is practically negligible. The situation is more or less the same when treated 30S subunit is allowed to associate with untreated 50S subunit. However, a somewhat different situation is observed when treated 50S subunit is allowed to associate with untreated 30S subunit. In this case, approximately 50% association is observed. Apparently 50% population of 50S subunits lose their association capacity on kethoxal treatment. Treatment with four times excess of kethoxal and also for longer time did not result in further loss of association capacity (results not presented). Subsequent experiments (described below) led to similar results indicating that this may be the distinct property of

50S ribosomes in contrast to 30S ribosomes. Eventually, it was established in this laboratory that 50S ribosomes derived from tight couple and loose couple ribosomes behave differently to kethoxal treatment^{15,16}.

Association capacities of 16S and 23S RNAs derived from kethoxal-treated 30S and 50S subunits : 16S and 23S RNAs were isolated by phenol method from 30S and 50S subunits which were earlier individually treated with kethoxal. The association capacities of the isolated RNAs to form 16S.23S complex were tested by the ultracentrifugation method¹. The testing was done under reconstitution condition which does not allow the complex to dissociate. As expected, 16S and 23S RNAs derived from untreated 30S and 50S subunits, respectively, from a binary complex (Fig. 2). However, 16S RNA derived from treated 30S subunit fails to form any complex with 23S RNA derived from either untreated or treated 50S subunits. When 23S RNA isolated from treated 50S subunit is used an interesting situation is observed. Unlike 16S RNA, approximately 50% of the population form the complex while remaining 50% remain unassociated or, in other words, isolated 16S and 23S RNAs behave in the same way as 30S and 50S subunits, as far as their association capacities are concerned.

Retention of association capacities of 16S and 23S RNAs derived from kethoxal-treated 70S ribosomes : That the association capacities of 30S and 50S

subunits are not affected when 70S ribosomes (tight couple) are treated with kethoxal has already been demonstrated by Noller and coworkers^{11,14}. This has also been verified in this laboratory by light scattering method (results not presented). Identical association curves were obtained with untreated subunits as well as the subunits derived from kethoxal-treated 70S ribosomes. 16S and 23S RNAs were isolated from the subunits and their association capacities were tested by ultracentrifugation method (Fig. 3). It is clear from the results that 16S and 23S RNAs fully retain their association capacities like their parent subunits. It does not matter whether one of the pair or both of them are derived from treated ribosomes. Thus, the protection of guanine bases of ribosomal subunits in the intact 70S ribosomes is selected in the isolated RNAs so far as their association capacities are concerned.

Loss of association capacities of 16S and 23S RNAs on treatment with kethoxal : In order to find out the effect of kethoxal treatment directly on the isolated RNAs, 16S and 23S RNAs were individually treated with kethoxal under two different conditions, (i) TEM buffer condition under which they do not associate with each other and (ii) reconstitution (R') condition under which they are capable of associating with each other. It is clear from the results presented in Fig. 4A that naked 16S RNA treated under any of the two conditions completely loses its capacity to associate with 23S RNA,

Fig. 2. Association capacities of 16S and 23S RNAs isolated from kethoxal-treated 30S and 50S subunits, as measured by density gradient centrifugation. ³²P-labelled 50S and 30S subunits were individually treated with kethoxal in TEM as described in the legend to Fig. 1. After treatment those were precipitated with ethanol and the corresponding RNAs extracted and purified. Equimolar amounts of ³²P-16S and ³²P-23S RNAs were mixed under reconstitution condition (R Buffer). Aliquot (0.5 ml) containing 2 × 10⁴ counts/min was layered on the top of 5 ml of 5-20% sucrose gradient in R buffer. Each of the fractions of 0.3 ml collected from the bottom was treated with 10% trichloroacetic acid and filtered through glass fibre filter (Whatman GF/3). The filters were dried and counted in LKB Rack Beta liquid scintillation counter. Symbol: (○) 16S and 23S RNAs isolated from untreated 30S and 50S subunits, (●) treated 30S and 50S subunits, (▽) treated 30S and untreated 50S and (□) untreated 30S and treated 50S.

Fig. 3. Association capacities of 16S and 23S RNAs isolated from kethoxal treated 70S ribosomes as measured by density gradient centrifugation. 32 P-labelled 70S ribosomes were treated with kethoxal and then dissociated into 50S and 30S subunits by dialysing against TMA buffer containing 0.1 mM Mg^{2+} . 32 P-labelled 23S and 16S RNAs were then isolated from the corresponding subunits and their association pattern observed under reconstitution condition (R buffer), as described in the legend to Fig. 2, by density gradient centrifugation. Symbol: (O) 16S and 23S RNAs derived from untreated 70S ribosome, (●) 16S from treated 70S and 23S from untreated 70S and (□) both from treated 70S.

whereas the 23S RNA on such treatment loses only about 50% of its capacity to associate with 16S RNA (Fig. 4B). Similar results were obtained in case of 16S and 23S RNAs isolated from kethoxal-treated 30S and 50S subunits, respectively (Fig. 2). Apparently, the treatment of RNAs at the subunit level or in the free state does not make any difference. Further, the treatment under dissociation condition or reconstitution condition produces the same effect.

Effect of treatment of 16S.23S RNA complex with kethoxal: It has already been mentioned that 30S and 50S subunits fully retain their association capacities when 70S ribosome is treated with kethoxal (results not presented). As demonstrated earlier (Fig. 3), 16S and 23S RNAs isolated from kethoxal-treated 70S ribosomes fully retain their association capacity. Therefore, it was of interest to find out what happens when 16S.23S complex is treated with kethoxal. So the complex in R' buffer was treated with kethoxal. After removal of kethoxal by dialysis against R buffer an aliquot was subjected to sucrose gradient centrifugation. It was observed that about 80% of the complex remained undissociated (Fig. 5B). The sample was then dissociated by dialysing against D buffer and subjected to sucrose gradient centrifugation in the same buffer. As expected, 16S and 23S RNAs dissociated fully. However, on retreatment with R buffer most of the RNA population (~80%) again associated indicating that the guanine moieties responsible for association are mostly protected

when the complex is treated with kethoxal. However, if a mixture of 16S and 23S RNAs is treated with kethoxal in TEM in which they do not associate, the RNAs are not capable of associating with each other (Fig. 5A). These results are also in strong favour of the assumption that the mechanism of association of 30S and 50S subunits is reflected in the association of naked 16S and 23S RNAs.

Discussion

As mentioned in the introduction, the primary object of the present work was to ascertain whether the complex formation between 16S and 23S RNAs reflects the mechanism involved in the association of 30S and 50S subunits under physiological condition. The approach has been comparatively simple based on the extensive studies already carried out by Noller and coworkers¹¹⁻¹⁴, in search of the mechanism of the association of the subunits. From the data on the protection of the specific guanine residues of rRNAs in the two subunits under the condition when they form tight couple, these authors justifiably hypothesised that certain specific regions of the two rRNAs might be involved in the mutual recognition by Watson-Crick base pairing or some other way. Since the complete sequence of the two RNAs are known, it was even possible to involve one or two specific regions in such recognition.

The work done by Noller and coworkers¹¹⁻¹⁴ has been of great help in designing our experiments.

Fig. 4. Effect of kethoxal treatment on 16S and 23S RNAs on their association capacities as measured by density gradient centrifugation. ³²P-labelled 16S and 23S RNAs were treated separately with kethoxal both in TEM buffer and R' buffer. Excess kethoxal was removed by dialysing against R buffer in both the cases and their association capacities measured by 5-20% sucrose gradient centrifugation in presence of R buffer after mixing with equimolar amount of nonradioactive complementary RNA. Symbol: (A) (○) 16S RNA treated in TEM buffer and (●) R' buffer; (B) (○) 23S RNA treated in TEM buffer and (●) R' buffer.

Fig. 5. Association of 16S and 23S RNAs derived from kethoxal treated 16S.23S complex, as measured by density gradient centrifugation. Equimolar mixture of ³²P-labelled 16S and 23S RNAs were treated with kethoxal in TEM buffer (A) and in R' buffer (B). In both the cases excess kethoxal was removed by dialysing against R buffer. Aliquots were subjected to 5-20% sucrose gradient centrifugation in R buffer (●). Both the sets were then dialysed for 12 h against RNA dissociation (D) buffer and then subjected to sucrose gradient centrifugation in the same (D) buffer (○). Finally, the samples were dialysed against R buffer for 12 h and to measure their association capacities aliquots were subjected to sucrose gradient centrifugation in R buffer (□).

Our main object was to find out the condition under which 30S and 50S subunits retain or lose their association capacities on kethoxal treatment and whether 16S and 23S RNAs isolated from such treated populations reflect similar situations when their own association is concerned. For the sake of convenience the results obtained have been summarised in Table 1 and surprisingly enough, 16S and 23S RNAs behave exactly in the same way as 30S and 50S subunits do. The treatment of 30S and 50S subunits with kethoxal and concomitant loss of association capacities do not unequivocally indicate whether only RNA-RNA interaction is involved in the association as a large number of proteins are present at the interface of the two subunits. In the association of 16S and 23S RNAs where nothing but RNA-RNA interaction can play a role, no such complication arises. The data can be justifiably extrapolated to assume that RNA-RNA interaction plays a major role in subunit association as well.

One disturbing feature of the results was that 30S subunit on treatment with kethoxal lost its association capacity completely but 50S subunit lost it only partially. This was also true for 16S and 23S RNAs isolated from the subunits. 16S RNA completely lost its capacity to associate with 23S RNA whereas 23S RNA lost approximately 50% of its capacity. This was also found to be true even when naked 16S and 23S RNAs are treated with kethoxal under either reconstitution condition or ordinary condition. It should be mentioned here that similar results were obtained by light scattering method. These results implied that there are not only two species of 50S ribosomes but also two species of 23S RNAs. The puzzle was solved when it was demonstrated in this laboratory that 50S ribosomes derived from tight and loose couple 70S ribosomes behaved differently to kethoxal treatment¹⁵. Tight couple 50S ribosomes which associate with 30S ribosomes at 4 mM Mg¹¹ ion completely

TABLE 1—RESULTS OF KETHOXAL TREATMENT

(A) Ribosome and subunits	Treatment with kethoxal and isolation methods	Association capacity with treated and untreated subunits		
		Full	Partial	Nil
(a)	$30S \xrightarrow{k} 30S^*$	—	—	50S, 50S*
(b)	$50S \xrightarrow{k} 50S^*$	—	80S	80S*
(c)	$70S \xrightarrow{k} 70S \begin{cases} \bullet \rightarrow 30S \\ \bullet \rightarrow 50S \end{cases}$	50S, 50S [●]	—	—
		30S, 30S [●]	—	—
(B) Ribosomal RNAs				
(i) Derived from kethoxal-treated ribosomes				
(d)	$30S \xrightarrow{k} 30S^* \rightarrow 16S^*$	—	—	23S, 23S*
(e)	$50S \xrightarrow{k} 50S^* \rightarrow 23S^*$	—	16S	16S*
(f)	$70S \xrightarrow{k} 70S \begin{cases} \bullet \rightarrow 30S \\ \bullet \rightarrow 50S \end{cases} \begin{cases} \bullet \rightarrow 16S \\ \bullet \rightarrow 23S \end{cases}$	23S, 23S [●]	—	—
		16S, 16S [●]	—	—
(ii) Directly treated with kethoxal				
(g)	$16S \begin{cases} \xrightarrow{k \text{ in TEM}} 16S^{\blacktriangle} \\ \xrightarrow{k \text{ in R}'} 16S^{\triangle} \end{cases}$	—	—	23S
		—	—	23S
(h)	$23S \begin{cases} \xrightarrow{k \text{ in TEM}} 23S^{\blacktriangle} \\ \xrightarrow{k \text{ in R}'} 23S^{\triangle} \end{cases}$	—	16S	—
		—	16S	—
(i)	$16S + 23S \begin{cases} \xrightarrow{k \text{ in TEM}} 16S^{\blacktriangle} + 23S^{\blacktriangle} \\ \xrightarrow{k \text{ in R}'} 16S^{\circ} \cdot 23S^{\circ} \end{cases}$	No association with each other. About 80% mutual association.		

Different symbols indicate different types of modification.

lost their association capacity on treatment with kethoxal whereas those derived from loose couple 70S ribosomes (which associate at higher Mg^{II} concentrations), remained unaffected. Subsequently it was shown in this laboratory that loose couple 50S ribosomes which were thought to be damaged ones^{21,22} are actually 'intermediate' in protein synthesis^{16,23}.

In this connection it should be mentioned that Noller and coworkers¹¹⁻¹⁴ found some interesting differences between 30S and 50S subunits on kethoxal treatment. In contrast to the extensive protection of sites of 16S RNA in 70S ribosomes¹¹ only two strongly protected sites were detected in 23S RNA¹⁴. On the basis of these results the authors concluded that the subunit association may involve contacts between single stranded sites in 16S RNA and 50S subunit proteins or non-Watson-Crick interaction with 23S RNA in addition to two suggested base-paired contacts. It should, however, be mentioned that six additional sites in 23S RNA are partially protected by 30S subunits. So there are some complications involved in such association.

The work is in progress in this laboratory to establish the points of contact between 16S and 23S RNAs.

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